

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF CHILDREN WITH MILD MENTAL RETARDATION IN SPECIAL VERSUS INCLUSIVE SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

International, National Legislation, Disability Acts and policies have also paved the way for children with special need education. They advocates of Special, Integrated and Inclusive education have highlighted the impact of special, integrated and inclusive education for the educable children with mental retardation(EMR). To keep in mind the researchers have decided to study between Special versus Inclusive Schools in Academic Achievement of Children with Mild Mental Retardation. The main objective was to study the influence of variables in the academic achievement of the children with mild mental retardation at special versus inclusive school. In this regard 20 mild mental retarded children were selected for the study in which 10 mild mentally retarded children were from special school and 10 mentally retarded children were from inclusive schools. The purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of sample. The standardized Functional Assessment Checklist Programme (FACP) was used to assess the academic performance of children with mild mental retardation. To know the comparison between special versus inclusive schools in the academic achievement of the children with mild mental retardation t-test was used for the present study. The t-test was applied to find whether there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special versus inclusive schools. The calculated t-test value is 0.736 which is less than

the table value of 2.101 at 5% level of significance; therefore there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special verses inclusive schools. Qualitatively the mean value of children in inclusive school is much better than special schools. Therefore inclusive schools are better in comparison to special schools.

Key words: special school, inclusive school, academic achievement, mild mental retardation

Introduction:

Mental retardation is a disability characterized by significant limitation both in intellectual functioning and in adaptive behavior as expressed in conceptual social and practical adaptive skills. Educable mentally retarded (EMR) children are those who are not able to be adequately educated in the regular schools. However, they can acquire sufficient knowledge and ability in the academic areas that are useful to function effectively in later life. They will be able to receive basic academic skills (reading, writing and arithmetic) and acquire self-help skill, which supports them to be socially and economically independent. Academic achievement refers to an acquired high-order ability to perform a task or an activity related to academic. Present study includes number, time, money, reading, writing, and functional academic as the components of academic skills. So the objectives of an educational programme for the educable group are same as the educational objectives for all children. They should be educated to make the greatest use of their abilities to satisfy their own needs as well as the demands of the society in which they are living.

The Special schools are generally organized according to different disability categories. We have schools for children with visual impairments (VI), for the intellectually challenged (MR) and for those with hearing impairments (HI). The major disadvantages of separate

education is separate environment and that the children may find it hard to readjust to their families, peers and communities and children and usually have to leave their families and communities to stay in a residential school because these schools are usually not available in their immediate environment. These special schools however, can play an active role in providing resource support for the mainstream schools by giving their specialized service.

Inclusion of children with disabilities in all aspects of schooling that other children are able to access and enjoy with the same recourse. It involves regular schools and classrooms genuinely adapting and changing to meet the needs of all children, as well as celebrating and valuing differences. This definition does not imply that children with diverse abilities will not receive specialized assistance or teaching outside of the classrooms when required, but rather that this is just one of many options that are available to, and are required of all children. There are few studies on comparison of special, integrated and inclusive schools. **Nugent (2007)** compares inclusive and special schools for children with Dyslexia. This study evaluates and compares special educational services for children with dyslexia. It was noted that, while parents expressed a preference for inclusive schools in theory, in reality, once provided with services, parents were actually more satisfied with specialist special schools. The discussion considers the implications of these findings in the context of the inclusion debate in special education. **Mani & Manivannan (2004)** studied that a single model educational programme is not suitable for all children with learning disabilities living in different areas. The factors such as culture, transportation, nature of disability, age, sex, etc., influence selection of suitable models, which provide right remediation through right strategies with right materials and technology in right time and in right place, make education of the children with learning disabilities as gainful as that of non-disabled children. **Punani (1994)** studied the

effectiveness as well as merits and demerits of various modes of education of the visually impaired children. The finding of the study is integrated education is no more a matter of option it is a compulsion, which can be accomplished at a comparatively lower social integration. Another, study on special versus regular school placement was selected for use in a meta-analysis. Special classes were found to be significantly inferior to regular class placement for students with below average IQs, and significantly superior to regular classes for behaviorally disordered, emotionally disturbed, and learning-disabled children.

Need of the Study:

- Though, both special and inclusive schools are equally important, yet there seems to exist significant difference in their mode of delivering the activity.
- Since decision makers (Parents, Teachers & Para-professionals) in the education of children with mild mental retardation face contradictory opinions, the study of service delivery models is imperative and felt as the need of the hour.

Objectives of the Study:

- To compare the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special verses inclusive schools
- To study the influence of variables in the development of academic skill of the sample.

Hypothesis:

Ho1 There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special verses inclusive schools.

Methodology:

The present study aims comparing the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special versus inclusive schools. Hence, the investigator selected mixed research design with purposive sampling technique. For, the conduction of the present study two different types of schools namely special and inclusive school was selected from Coimbatore district. The sample was selected from three special schools and four inclusive schools. Sample size is 10 children with mild mental retardation were chosen each from special and inclusive schools. Hence, the total sample size constituted 20 children with mild mental retardation.

Tools:

In the context of the present study, it is required for the researcher to assess the academic achievement of the sample in two different educational setups namely special and inclusive schools. The investigator selected checklist as the tool for the study. The standardized tool Functional Assessment Checklist Programming (FACP) developed by National Institute for the Mentally Handicapped (NIMH) at primary-I level was selected. There are seven domains in this tool but researcher chosen only 40 items of academic domain. To assess the items of the tools, the investigator prepared and also collected appropriate materials for direct observation. After, establishing sufficient rapport with the sample, the investigator requested to the subjects to perform the activities of the tool one by one with the help of materials prepared. Through, keen observation of the performance of the sample, the investigator made an assessment in the tool. Thus the data was collected for the study.

The collected data was tabulated and consolidated for further statistical treatment. The grouped data was subjected to quantitative analysis, using t-test. The testing of hypothesis is as follows-

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special verses inclusive schools.

T-test comparison between the academic achievements of children with mild mental retardation in special verses inclusive schools.

Service delivery model	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Special School	10	24.4000	11.2368
Inclusive School	10	27.5000	7.1375

T-test for Equality of Means

t	df	Sig.
0.736	18	Ns

Discussion:

The t-test was applied to find whether there is a significant difference in academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special verses inclusive schools. The calculated t-test value is 0.736 which is less than the table value of 2.101 at 5% level of significance. Since, the calculated value is less than the table values it is inferred that there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special verses inclusive schools. Hence the hypothesis is retained.

Conclusion:

The main purpose of the investigator in this research is, to find out the better educational setups in the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation. The performance of children in both type of school like special and inclusive is the almost same. So, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation in special verses inclusive schools. It is evident that from the above research studies that there is no much difference in academic achievement of children with mild mental retardation. But the children who have studied in inclusive school showed high mean value of academic achievement, when compared with special school. So, inclusive school provides slightly better educational service for children with mild mental retardation. Our research also shows that inclusive school is providing better educational service delivery in present situation. Thus, inclusive school gives better educational service.

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